

From Trust to Betrayal: An Experimental Study on the Vulnerabilities and Factors Influencing Elderly Populations' Responses to Online Scams in Colombo, Sri Lanka

D.L. Ubeysiri

*Department of Information Technology, Faculty of Management Studies and Commerce
University of Sri Jayewardenepura, Sri Lanka
dulakshaubeyisiri@gmail.com*

Abstract

The rapid growth of digital communication and online financial services has elevated exposure to cyber facilitated fraud, particularly among elderly individuals who often face digital, cognitive and social vulnerabilities. Although previous research has explored the impacts of online scams, many studies rely on retrospective self-reports which provide minimal understanding of how elderly individuals make their decisions at the moment of scam exposure. This study addresses the gap by examining real time responses to online scams and the psychological and social factors that influence engagement and ignoring behaviors. An exploratory qualitative field experiment was conducted in the Colombo District of Sri Lanka, where elderly individuals use mobile phones and social media platform in their day today lives. A simulated investment scam containing institutional authority cues was shared via WhatsApp to reflect common scamming scenarios. Ten individuals aged 60 years and above were exposed to a message in their everyday digital environment, then followed by a debriefing session, informed consent and post semi structured interviews. Interview data were analyzed thematically to identify patterns in reasoning, emotional reactions and social influences. The findings show that engagement with the scam was attributed to low digital confidence, strong trust in authority cues, emotional vulnerability and limited opportunities for immediate social advice. In opposition, avoidance behavior was attributed to identifying red flags such as unknown sender details, poor message quality and urgency cues as well as prior exposure to scam awareness through loved ones or media. By examining responses close to the point of exposure, this study provides practical insights into how elderly individuals analyze and respond to online scams, informing the development of context sensitive and specific digital fraud prevention strategies.

Keywords: *Digital safety awareness, Elderly individuals, Online scams, Qualitative field experiment, Scam vulnerability*